

Impact of Reactor Cycle Length and MOX Fuel Fraction on Scenarios involving Plutonium Multirecycling with PWRs

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ABSTRACT

This paper investigates the influence of fuel management options on fuel cycle strategies that aim to multirecycle plutonium in pressurized water reactors (PWRs) using MOX-MR fuels. Plutonium recovered from the reprocessing of spent MOX fuel cannot be directly reused in new fuel fabrication, as its fissile quality is insufficient, leading to an excessively high plutonium content in the fresh fuel. Consequently, the fabrication of MOX-MR fuel relies on blending plutonium from both spent UOX and spent MOX fuels to restore an adequate fissile isotopic composition. As plutonium fissile quality is progressively degraded through successive recycling, the proportion of spent UOX fuel sent for reprocessing must increase to compensate for the decrease plutonium quality. This leads to a shortage of spent UOX fuels and limits the long-term plutonium stabilization within this fuel cycle. Reactor depletion simulations demonstrate that the plutonium content required in fresh MOX-MR fuels is strongly dependent on fuel management parameters, particularly the MOX-MR fraction in the core and the reactor cycle length. When the UOX fuel characteristics—such as uranium enrichment—are held constant, a reduction in the reactor cycle length results in lower plutonium content in fresh MOX-MR fuels. This mitigates the demand for spent UOX fuels and thereby enhances the overall sustainability of the MOX-MR strategy. This work highlights, once again, the fundamental trade-off between optimizing fuel cycle performance for plutonium and spent fuel stabilization and maintaining reactor performance through the efficient utilization of UOX fuels.

Keywords: Plutonium recycling, Fuel cycle, EPR, Fuel management, Irradiation length

1. INTRODUCTION

France's current strategy foresees the construction of new EPRs in the next decades that will enable plutonium and uranium multirecycling. After one first recycling, the plutonium from MOX spent fuels cannot be loaded in new fresh fuel as its fissile quality is too low leading to a plutonium content higher than the acceptable limit, often taken close to 12 % [1]. The solution proposed for MOX-MR fuels (MOX – MultiRecycled) is to blend the plutonium recovered from MOX spent fuel with plutonium from UOX spent fuel in order to correct the plutonium isotopic vector. MOX-MR technology is therefore very similar to MOX technology, which could allow a licensing agenda for this new type of fuel compatible with the implementation of plutonium multi-recycling in PWRs by 2050.

This strategy is studied by stakeholders within scenario simulation such as in [2] or in [3]. To cope the degradation of the plutonium isotopic vector after each recycling, the UOX stream at spent fuel treatment has to be increased. Therefore, this strategy is not sustainable as the amount of available spent UOX fuels becomes, at some point, not sufficient enough to maintain an acceptable isotopic vector in

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fresh MOX-MR fuels, as shown in [2]. The present work aims to see if some fuel management optimizations may increase the viability period by investigating the impact of the reactor cycle length. Two fuel management options are studied in this work. The first one considers EPRs loaded with approximately 50 % of MOX-MR fuels such as in [4]. The second considers only 30 % of MOX-MR such as in current PWRs, loaded with MOX fuels in French reactors. The scenario study is performed with the CLASS package [5] with dedicated reactor models, presented in [6], built for those two fuel management options and summarized in this paper.

The first part details the reactor depletion simulations performed to build databases needed for modeling fresh fuel fabrication in CLASS. The core configurations are detailed and the model explained. This part ends with a discussion of the importance of the reactor cycle length (also called here irradiation time) on the plutonium content of fresh MOX-MR fuel according to the plutonium isotopic vector. The second part presents scenario simulations of an academic representation of the French fleet. For this work, the focus is made on the time when UOX spent fuel stockpile is not sufficient to feed the fabrication of new MOX-MR fuels, representing the time where the MOX-MR strategy has to be adapted.

2. REACTOR MODELING FOR FUEL CYCLE SIMULATIONS

To study the potentialities and limitations of MOX-MR fuel management for plutonium multirecycling with different fuel cycle simulators, models are needed since direct coupling with core depletion simulations would be very costly. Difficulties arise with fresh fuel fabrication simulations. Indeed, the isotopic composition of plutonium inside different spent fuels is unknown and the plutonium content of fresh fuel has to be adapted in accordance, to ensure reactor criticality during the scheduled irradiation time. The Fuel Loading Model (FLM) in fuel cycle simulators aims to identify this fresh fuel composition. To do so, some reactor properties have to be estimated as a function of the plutonium content and its isotopic composition in fresh MOX fuels. Those estimations are performed with artificial neural networks, trained on a dedicated database, built for this work.

This section presents firstly the core configurations built for this work. The chosen calculation scheme to ensure a good compromise between accuracy and numerical cost is detailed, then the core loading patterns are presented. In a second subsection, the training of neural networks is presented as well as their use for the FLM construction. Finally, the impact of the irradiation time, criterion chosen to adapt the plutonium content at each core refueling is studied.

2.1. Core configuration

2.1.1. Calculation scheme

As hundreds of calculations are needed to build a single reactor depletion database, the calculation scheme has to be efficient, that is to say precise but numerically frugal. For the purpose of this study, core level simulations are needed, requiring a two-level calculation scheme. Lattice calculations are performed with APOLLO2 [7] with the REL2005 recommendations [8], using JEFF3.3 nuclear data library. Two group diffusion cross-sections are homogenized on a pin-by-pin discretization, tabulated as a function of the burn-up, the coolant density and the fuel temperature. CRONOS2 [9] solves the diffusion equation at each time step at the core level using those tabulated macroscopic data. An internal thermo-hydraulic coupling allows to compute the complete temperature distribution at the pin level. More details as well as the performance of this calculation scheme can be found in previous works [10].

2.1.2. Loading pattern construction

The core configurations built for this work are greatly inspired from the work of Rugama and Spaggiari [4]. In that work, 4 different assemblies are considered, 3 UOX with different number of pins enriched with gadolinium and 1 MOX. In order to simplify the seek of an acceptable loading pattern, only 2 different UOX fuels were considered here, conserving the total number of fuel pins with gadolinium at the core level. Two different MOX fraction were considered for the different loading pattern: firstly

approximately 50 % of MOX fuel in accordance of [4] and a variation with the replacement of 16 MOX assemblies per UOX ones to reach approximately 30 % MOX in the core.

Figure 1. Loading pattern built for this work

The identification of the loading patterns used for this work and presented in Figure 1 relies on a try and test approach. Some depletion simulations are performed with a given MOX isotopic composition taken from [4] and reminded in Table I. The loading pattern is adapted, looking at hot spots (assemblies that deliver too much power), while the assembly power factor is not considered acceptable during the whole evolution. This power factor, also quoted F_{2D} in the following, is defined as the maximal value over the reactor evolution of the ratio of the power delivered by one assembly over the average power of all assemblies. An acceptable value often quoted by operational specialist would be under 1.45. The cycle lengths calculated with our calculation scheme, our loading pattern and the reference plutonium composition are respectively 14.3 and 15.2 GWd/t for the 50 % and the 30 % fuel management studied here. Those values seem close enough from [4] to be considered acceptable.

Table I. Reference plutonium isotopic vector taken from [4]

Plutonium content	238Pu	239Pu	239Pu	241Pu	242Pu	241Am
9 %	3.44	46.80	29.66	8.04	10.60	1.46

2.2. Fuel loading models

The methodology chosen to build the fuel loading model is the one detailed in [6]. It relies on an inversion algorithm to identify the fresh fuel composition that allows the considered reactor to sustain the chain reaction during the targeted irradiation time. The consideration of a small tolerance of this target value allows to link the plutonium content in fresh fuel to its isotopic quality (defined as the ratio of fissile nuclei in the fuel) as a constant step function for one given irradiation length. To build this constant step function, 5000 fresh compositions are calculated to reach a given irradiation time, then a gathering process is performed to ensure a minimal deviation between the target for irradiation time and the actual value. To do so, artificial neural networks (ANN) are built in order to estimate the irradiation time as a function of the fresh fuel composition.

2.2.1. Depletion database construction and artificial neural network training

500 initial fresh fuel compositions were sampled using the Latin Hyper Square (LHS) sampling technique and 500 depletion calculations were performed with our calculation scheme allowing to compute power factor, irradiation time and average discharge burn-up of each type of assemblies. The sampling phase space is reminded in Table II covering all composition of possible MOX fresh fuel. This

database is then split in two independent one: the first one of 400 random simulations is called the training database and is used to train ANN with the TMVA library [11] for each of the previously quoted observables. The second sample of 100 reactor evolution simulations, called the testing database, is used to quantify properly estimation biases of each ANN. Each ANN configuration is adapted while the precision isn't lower than numerical bias of the depletion calculation scheme. ANN configurations and precisions are presented in Table III.

Table II. Plutonium isotopic vector sample.

	Plutonium content	238Pu	239Pu	241Pu	242Pu	241Am
Min (%)	5.3	0.7	40.0	2.0	4.0	0.0
Max (%)	12.0	5.0	65.0	14.0	12.0	3.0

Table III. ANN architecture (number of hidden layers and neurons per layer) and precision

	Architecture	Standard deviation of estimation
Irradiation time	(4,4)	0.26 %
F_{2D}	(16,16)	0.17 %
UOX discharge BU	(4,4)	0.04 %
MOX discharge BU	(4,4)	0.19 %

2.2.2. Model construction

The built ANN are used to identify the plutonium content needed in fresh MOX fuels to sustain the irradiation time as a function of the plutonium isotopic composition. 5000 new fresh isotopic vectors are sampled within the phase space described in Table II. The plutonium content needed to reach the wanted value for irradiation time (14.3 GWd/t for EPR 50 % MOX and 15.2 for EPR 30 %) is calculated for those 5000 isotopic compositions. The results for the EPR 50 % are depicted in Figure 2 (a), that presents all the computed plutonium contents as a function of their fissile quality in blue. Given the sensitivity of the irradiation time to the plutonium content, and given the possible variation of irradiation times due to operational conditions (such as stretch out or load following), a tolerance of 0.3 GWd/t on the target value for irradiation time was considered to build a constant step function such as in [6]. Intervals of fissile quality are considered and a new plutonium content is calculated for each interval to minimize the deviation of each cycle length compared to the reference value. This leads to a constant step function describing the plutonium content needed to ensure the irradiation time as a function of the plutonium quality, presented in Figure 2 (a) by the orange dots. The actual deviation of the cycle length is presented in Figure 2 (b), showing a small deviation (the std value is close to 0.3 GWd/t).

2.3. Irradiation length impact

The same process was repeated for several target values for irradiation times varying from 14 GWd/t to 16.5 GWd/t in order to build, for each fuel management, this relationship that links the plutonium content to its isotopic quality for fresh fuel simulations in fuel cycle scenarios. Results, presented in Figure 3, show a great dependency of the plutonium content to the irradiation time, especially for the EPR 30 % MOX. Indeed, reducing the irradiation time, and then the average discharge burn-up of assemblies, would lead to a smaller plutonium content for the same fissile quality. Also, it is possible to build fresh fuel using more degraded plutonium with a lower irradiation time as the limit of 12 % is reached for smaller plutonium quality. Reducing the irradiation time would imply a deterioration of core performances as UOX fuels could reach higher burn-up.

Figure 2. (a) Plutonium content of MOX-MR fresh fuels as a function of its fissile quality for an irradiation time of 14.3 GWd/t for the EPR 50 % MOX fuel management. In orange, are the average value over a given fissile quality interval that minimise the deviation among this interval. (b) Actual deviation of the irradiation time (in GWd/t) between a plutonium content given by the constant step function and the reference value.

Figure 3. Fuel Loading Models for the two fuel management options, as a function the target value for the reactor cycle length.

The consequence of this irradiation time variation should be reflected in power factors that are presented in Figure 4 for the 5000 isotopic compositions and the 2 studied fuel management. It shows an increase of the value that however seems manageable.

The Figure 5 shows the difference between the discharge burn-up of UOX fuels against MOX fuels, due to the variation of this target value, showing the relevance of our fuel fabrication model as this difference is close to 0 for the reference values (15.3 GWd/t for EPR 30 % MOX and 14.2 GWd/t for EPR 50 % MOX). Decreasing the irradiation length would then lead to lose the energy equivalence between UOX and MOX, even though it may have benefit impacts on the fuel cycle for plutonium multi-recycling in EPR using MOX-MR fuels.

Figure 4. Impact of the irradiation length on the 2D power factor

Figure 5. Impact of the irradiation length on the energy equivalence between UOX and MOX. This equivalence is quantified with the difference of discharged burn-up between UOX and MOX fuel assemblies.

3. FUEL CYCLE SIMULATION WITH CLASS

3.1. Scenario definition

The study case for the investigation of the impact of the reactor cycle length in the sustainability of the MOX-MR strategy is inspired from the French fleet evolution already presented in [12]. It considers the deployment of 30 new EPRs between 2037 and 2065. The first load of MOX-MR fuels is planned in 2050. Whereas the work presented in [12] considered a fix plutonium content among the whole scenario, in this work, the plutonium content in fresh MOX-MR fuels is adapted according the plutonium quality and the relations depicted in Figure 3. As a result, the plutonium content is not constant among the scenario evolution but is a result of the simulations. The mixing fraction of different plutonium source for fresh fuel fabrication is kept constant (approximately 40 % of plutonium coming from spent UOX fuels) and material flows at treatment are adapted to guarantee those fractions.

The number of EPRs loaded with MOX-MR fuels are adapted to insure a plutonium stabilization. Our calculations shows that 15 and 24 EPRs loaded with MOX-MR assemblies are needed for this goal, respectively for the fuel management options EPR 50 % MOX-MR and EPR 30 % MOX-MR. Those

numbers of reactors actually lead approximately to the same global number of MOX-MR assemblies in the fleet (1860 for EPR 50% and 1776 for EPR 30%). Two reactor cycle length have been considered 14 GWd/t and 15 GWd/t leading to average discharge burn-up of 42 GWd/t and 45 GWd/t. Due to the strong difference between UOX and MOX-MR average discharge burn-up for the EPR 30 % MOX-MR at 42 GWd/t, seen in Figure 5 (a), the scenario results involving this hypothesis are not studied here.

3.2. Scenario results

As said in the introduction, the MOX-MR strategy is not sustainable as it leads to a shortage of UOX spent fuels, needed to recover good quality plutonium for MOX-MR fresh fuel fabrication. The observable used here to quantify the increase in the viability of the MOX-MR strategy by optimizing fuel management is the first year in which a shortage of UOX fuel is observed. Due to the different FLMS represented in Figure 3, it is expected that a shorter irradiation time leads to a greater UOX shortage date as the plutonium content in fresh fuel is expected to be greater. Figure 6 presents the results obtained considering the two core configurations. Figure 6 (a) shows the plutonium inventory. Because of a longer transition, the case with 24 EPRs 30 % MOX shows a higher inventory. Figure 6 (b) presents the evolution of spent UOX fuel stock pile and shows that the improvement is actually significant as the shortage of UOX spent fuels occurs before 2070 when considering a discharge burnup of 45 GWd/t (and a reactor cycle length of 15 GWd/t) whereas the reduction to a target of 42 GWd/t (with a reactor cycle length of 14 GWd/t) would lead to a shortage after 2080. In the case of EPRs 30 %, the shortage of plutonium coming from UOX is actually latter than the scenario time horizon.

(a) Total plutonium inventory in the fuel cycle

(b) Heavy nuclei mass in spent UOX fuel stock pile

Figure 6. Scenario results considering the deployment of 15 EPRs loaded with 50 % MOX-MR fuels

4. CONCLUSIONS

This paper presents possible improvement of the sustainability of the MOX-MR strategy, thanks to fuel management optimizations. It has been shown in the literature that this strategy is not sustainable due to a shortage of high-quality plutonium, provided by UOX spent fuel. The fraction of MOX-MR fuel assemblies in the all fleet, needed for plutonium inventory stabilization, is too high compared to the need of UOX spent fuel at treatment to guarantee an acceptable plutonium fissile quality. Optimizing the fuel management options may decrease the plutonium content at constant fissile quality or decrease the acceptable quality at constant plutonium content.

Investigating core fuel management influence on fuel cycle simulations implies adequate reactor models in fuel cycle simulators that take into account the physics at the core level. A dedicated calculation scheme was developed to perform 3D reactor depletion evolutions. It was used to find acceptable loading pattern for two different fuel management: with 30 % and with 50 % MOX-MR fuels. Depletion simulations databases were built for both of these MOX-MR fractions varying the fresh MOX-MR composition, keeping constant the UOX assemblies. Artificial Neural Networks were trained to estimate reactor cycle length, assembly power factors and average discharged burn-up of UOX and

MOX-MR fuels. Those neural networks are used to compute the plutonium content of fresh fuels according to its isotopic composition to ensure reactor criticality over the wanted reactor irradiation time. Considering a tolerance over this target value has led us to propose a constant step function to link the plutonium content to its fissile quality for a given irradiation time.

Building those constant step relations for several reactor cycle length shows a strong dependance of the plutonium content to this parameter. Reducing the reactor cycle length leads to accept lower plutonium quality for fresh fuel fabrication, or leads to smaller plutonium content at constant quality. The impact of this parameter on a complete scenario was assessed on an academic version of the French nuclear fleet deploying 30 EPRs by 2065, some of them loaded with MOX-MR fuels to stabilize the plutonium inventory. Simulations show that the viability time of the MOX-MR strategy is strongly impacted by this reactor irradiation time parameters. It is then possible to optimize the fuel cycle for plutonium management at the expense of the reactor performances. Indeed, longer viability time are obtained with reduced reactor irradiation time leading to more frequent reloading.

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